

INCREDIBLE

Innovation Networks of Cork, Resins and Edibles in the Mediterranean basin

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Thematic Networks compiling knowledge ready for practice

D3.6 – Dissemination Material from Cross-Cutting Seminar (1st)

Integrating NWFPs in Territorial Marketing and Ecosystem Service value chains

10-11, May, Albareto (PR), Italy

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Structure of the document

The deliverable, produced by Etifor, aims to summarize main contents and inputs emerged during the cross-cutting Seminar (CCS), held in Borgo Val di Taro (Italy) at the beginning of May 2019. In the context of INCREDIBLE project, each CCS aims to create cross-sectorial partnerships and supporting NWFP actors and practitioners in the development of innovative solutions for NWFP management.

The present document, in the first part (up to page 14), **aims to supply an overview of the event**, providing the main objectives, the agenda, the list of attendees, a summary of presentations held during the event and main take-home messages.

Whereas, **main outputs and conclusions of the event are presented through an infographic** (page 15). Furthermore, the four best practices presented during the event are **summarized through factsheets** (according to the format developed in Task 2.1) and **infographics**, from page 16 onwards.

The factsheets included in this deliverable will be published in the Knowledge Repository for Non-Wood Forest Products (<https://repository.incredibleforest.net>). Before the on-line factsheet publication, minor changes may be introduced in the version of the factsheets present in this document.

The infographics included in this deliverable will be published in the INCREDIBLE project website (<https://incredibleforest.net>).

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1. Foreword of the first CCS

The cross-cutting Seminar (CCS) held in Italy focused on the wider integration of NWFPs with local rural development agendas by developing a set of marketing tools for supporting clusters of NWFP to promote the whole territory, building an attractive brand. The event was organized at Borgo Val di Taro, that hosts one of the case studies presented during the event (*Fungo di Borgotaro I.G.P.*)

In detail, “*Fungo di Borgotaro I.G.P.*” is the first European trademark related to a forest product and is dated back to 1996. Due to its unicity and thanks to a well-coordinated territorial marketing strategy, the Taro valley attracts annually thousands of tourists and mushroom pickers and lovers. Mushrooms are so relevant for the Taro valley that even the forest management has as its main objective the mushroom production. *Consorzio Comunalie Parmensi* is the public entity that manages the public properties that have an extension of roughly 13,000ha.

2. Agenda of the CCS

PROGRAM 1ST DAY: 10/05/2019

Location: Palafungo, via A. Gotelli, 9, 43051, Albareto (PR)

Integrating NWFPs in Territorial Marketing and Ecosystem Service value chains	
10:00	Welcome and registration
10:30	Introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Davide Riccoboni: Mayor Comune di Albareto • Pietro Oieni: Director, Ministry of Agriculture, food and tourism (MIPAAFT) • Roberto Dellapina: President of Consorzio Comunalie Parmensi Presentation of INCREDIBLE project (ETIFOR)
11:00	Non wood forest products: the importance for the territory and the community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrico Vidale: Mushrooms and truffles market in Italy: past, present and future • Nicola Sitta: State of the art of the Italian wild berries market • Sara Maltoni: Italian cork and aromatic & medicinal plants market
12:00	The new Italian fiscal reform on NWFPs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Enrico Vidale: new Italian fiscal law of NWFPs: present and future of the sector
12:30	Speed date lunch: B2B and B2experts in Territorial marketing of NWFPs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nicola Sitta, Mycologist and wild berries expert ○ Sara Covi: Strada della mela e dei sapori delle valli di Non e di Sole ○ Carlo Marena: Save the Truffles
14:00	Territorial Marketing related to NWFPs: best cases show <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Diego Gallo: Tourism and NWFPs ○ Sara Covi: Strada della mela e dei sapori delle valli di Non e di Sole ○ Antonio Mortali: Consorzio IGP Borgo Val di Taro ○ Carlo Marena: Save the truffles
15:30	Break

15:50	<p>Round table: Integrating NWFPs in territorial marketing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maria Capecchi: Responsible of the truffle sector in Emilia Romagna Region • Pierluigi Fedele: Captain of Carabinieri forest Corp of Parma • Diego Gallo: expert in territorial Marketing and responsible tourism • Sara Covi: Strada della mela e dei sapori delle valli di Non e di Sole • Enzo Valbonesi: Responsible of the mushroom sector in Emilia Romagna Region
17:00	End of work

Table 1. Agenda of the first day.

PROGRAM 2nd DAY: 11/05/2019

FIELD TRIP Integrating NWFP in Territorial Marketing and Ecosystem Service value chains	
10:00	Welcome and registration
10:15	<p>Trekking lead by Antonio Mortali, Forest expert and natural and environmental guide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mycosilviculture • Management techniques to boost NWFPs production • Integrating NWFPs in territorial marketing • Multifunctionality of the forest • Tourism in the forest • The role of the Natural Guide <p>Lunch: organized in a mountain hut, managed by Comunalie di Sevola-Revoletto, Comune di Bedonia</p>
16:30	End of the day

Table 2. Agenda of the fieldtrip.

3. Attendees

1 st day – The seminar			
Name and surname	Position	Organisation	Region and country
Jacopo Giacomoni		ETIFOR	Italy
Nicola Andrighetto		ETIFOR	Italy
Enrico Vidale		UNIPD	Italy
Antonio Mortali		Consorzio Comunalie Parmensi	Italy
Roberto Dellapina		Consorzio Comunalie Parmensi	Italy
Nicola Sitta		Freelance	Italy
Sara Maltoni		FORESTAS	Italy
Sara Covi		Strada della Mela e dei Sapori delle Valli di Non e di Sole	Italy
Carlo Marena		Save the truffle	Italy
Diego Gallo		ETIFOR	Italy
Maria Capecchi		Regione Emilia Romagna	Italy
Gabriele Locatelli		Regione Emilia Romagna	Italy
Pierluigi Fedele		Corpo Carabinieri	Italy
Anton Brenko		CFRI	Croatia
Dino Bursic		CFRI	Croatia

Olivia Marois		CRPF	France
Eduard Mauri		EFI	Spain
Maurizio Savi		Ass. Provinciale Tartufai Placentini	Italy
Davide Biciocchi		Ass. Provinciale Tartufai Piacentini	Italy
Renzo Bosi		Comunalia Boschetto	Italy
Francesca Coloni		ASL Bologna	Italy
Carlo Comini		Ranca Tartufi SRL	Italy
Bruno Sabella		CRATER	Italy
Remo Battini		CFRET	Italy
Dario Brattesani		Comunalia	Italy
Ilaria Bertolotti		Borgolab srl.	Italy
Elio Covi		Raccoglitore	Italy
Andrea Tramelli		Gal del Ducato	Italy
Maura Riccoboni		Gela PR	Italy
Roberto Porcacchia		Corpo carabinieri Forestali	Italy
Luciana Sabini		Assessore commune Albareto	Italy
Angela Feroi		Consorzio Comunalie	Italy
Miriam Taburoni		Consorzio Comunalie	Italy
Giuliana Soarpenti		Consorzio Comunalie	Italy
Gianni Petrizzoli		Regola di Costa	Italy
Domenico Bernardo		Consorzio Comunalie Parmensi	Italy
Giovanni Motol		Consorzio Comunalie Parmensi	Italy
Antonio Mortali		Consorzio Fungo Borgotaro	Italy
Giuseppe Andreatta		Libero professionista	Italy
Walter Gavazzini		Raccoglitore I.G.P. porcino	Italy
Filippo Vazza		Azienda Agricola Tre Ri.	Italy
Luigi Paganini		Paganini SRL	Italy
Enrico Adami		Paganini SRL	Italy
Enrico Delucchi		Dirigente Agricoltura	Italy
Ivo Botti		Tecnico forestale	Italy
Ivo Bertorelli		Presidente Consorzio "La Rocchetta"	Italy
Anna Sarcletti			Italy
Federica Lucchi			Italy
Riccardo Bonanti		Azienda Agricola	Italy
Alberto Chiappari		Confagricoltura Parma	Italy
2nd Day – Field Trip			
Name and surname	Position	Organisation	Region and country
Jacopo Giacomoni		ETIFOR	Italy
Enrico Vidale		UNIPD	Italy
Antonio Mortali		Consorzio Fungo Borgotaro	Italy
Sara Maltoni		FORESTAS	Italy
Maria Capecchi		Regione Emilia Romagna	Italy
Anton Brenko		CFRI	Croatia
Dino Bursic		CFRI	Croatia
Olivia Marois		CNPF	France
Eduard Mauri		EFI	Spain
Maddalena Senter		AUSF Padova	Italy
Gianni Petrizzoli		Regola di Costa	Italy
Valerio Snichelotto		AUSF Padova	Italy
Ettore Mitali		UNIPD	Italy

Giacomo Pagot		UNIPD	Italy
Francesco Sforza		AUSF Padova	Italy
Alessia Marchetto		AUSF Padova	Italy
Sara Vigolo		AUSF Padova	Italy
Mariachiara Cravero		AUSF Padova	Italy
Enrico Fortin		AUSF Padova	Italy
Riccardo Bordiga		AUSF Padova	Italy
Matteo Varotto		AUSF Padova	Italy
Camilla Marzolo		AUSF Padova	Italy
Giovanni Raffaelli		AUSF Padova	Italy
Gabriele Longo		AUSF Padova	Italy
Jacopo Altero		AUSF Padova	Italy
Lorenzo Venturini		AUSF Padova	Italy
Marco Vanotti		Student UNIPD	Italy
Maria Vittoria Luchesa		Student UNIPD	Italy

Table 3. List of attendees to the first cross-cutting seminar in Borgo Taro.

4. Main contents of the seminar

4.1 A summary of presentations of the first day

Morning

Enrico Vidale: *Mushrooms and truffles market in Italy: past, present and future*

The biggest problem of the Italian mushroom and truffle sector is the lack of data, that doesn't allow the development of reliable studies and appropriate policies for the sector. The Italian mushroom market has historically played an import role in the international market, characterized by a huge export. Nevertheless, the national market has recently seen a reduction of the national production and, therefore, Italy, in the last years, became a net importer. One of the most relevant problems that affect the national situation is the relevant role covered by the informal market. Recently some positive signals arrived from the National Forest department, that is putting an effort to regulate and de-tax both mushroom and truffle sector, as confirmed by the recently approved fiscal reform. Also, the Italian truffle sector has historically very appealing also abroad, with some world famous "Made in Italy" productions. Nevertheless, in the last decades, there was a strong international competition and, also due to weak national strategies, competitors such as Spain, Hungary, and Turkey are weakening the Italian leadership. There is the urgent need to reform national strategies and policies, and the already mentioned fiscal law can be considered definitely a starting point for improving the sector.

Nicola Sitta: *State of the art of the Italian wild berries market and a brand for the promotion of local berries*

Best case described through factsheet and infographic (page 19-21)

According to national regulation on berries, each Italian region has the duty to regulate the sector through local laws. This fact creates complexity and heterogeneity, representing a limiting factor for the proper development of the sector. In the Emilian Apennine, the harvesting of bilberries has a strong tradition since there are a relevant number of "vaccinieti", the ecosystems where bilberries naturally grow. In detail, some area of Apennines presents the ecological conditions for the development of "*Vaccinium myrtillus*", a wild species of bilberry. Unlikely, most of the final consumers are not able to distinguish the different varieties of bilberries and if they are cultivated or wild. In order to support the promotion of local wild bilberries, the Modena Chamber of Trade introduced the Brand "*Mirtillo Nero dell'appennino Modenese*". Pickers and local companies that want to sell bilberries with this brand have to follow specific regulations and standards. This is an interesting marketing strategy and nowadays:

- **9 local enterprise** (mainly focus on transformation) currently can utilize the label promoted by the local chamber of commerce;
- **141 pickers were registered** for the professional harvesting,
- **360,000 €** is the annual value of wild bilberries harvested and traded by companies, that can use the trademark.

Sara Maltoni: *Italian cork market*

Cork is a multi-purpose material, that can be used in the construction sector, as well as a wine stopper, fashion design, and several other applications. The Iberian Peninsula represents by far the most developed Mediterranean hotspot for cork production. Also, in Italy there are almost 170,000 ha of cork forests, and most of them are in Sardinia. Some of the challenges that the Italian cork

sector is facing are the land abandonment, the competition with alternative agricultural crops, the climate change and the loss of traditional knowledge (especially related to harvesting techniques). In economic terms, the Italian cork production has increased from around 150 million € in 2011 to 243 million € in 2017. Nevertheless, with a broader view, it can be observed that from the '60 the role of Italy in the international market decreased significantly. Furthermore, in the last decades, the transformation industry faced a big decrease, especially after the global crisis in 2008. The main causes of the cork crisis in Italy are the high extraction and harvesting cost and the fiscal regime not in line with European competitor (e.g. 22% VAT in Italy and 6% VAT in Portugal).

Enrico Vidale: *The new Italian fiscal reform on NWFPs*

The Italian law n.145 dated 30 Dec 2018, introduced new parameters for the fiscal regime related to NWFPs, with special regard to duties of non-professional and professional pickers. One of the goals of the law is the reduction of fiscal pressure on pickers in order to contrast the diffusion of the black market in the sector. The law has introduced a yearly license of 100 € for non-professional pickers, and this license represents the only tax to sell mushroom and truffles up to 7,000 €. Besides, the law can have positive impacts, in terms of traceability and related promotion of local products.

Lunch with speed date B2B and B2Experts activity

In order to facilitate information sharing, during the lunch, several tables were organized, where the participants had the chance to discuss with speakers and experts. In fact, in traditional conferences, the participants may have time to ask some question, but usually, do not have the chance to discuss face to face with experts and speakers. In this speed date activity, experts, companies, technicians, public entities and all the other participants had the chance to sit in small tables (4-5 people) and discuss about NWFPs and territorial marketing. The activity organized was appreciated, and the tables were utilized during all lunch-time, with turnover at the different tables.

Afternoon

Technical note: During the presentations of the afternoon, a software called Sli.do (<https://www.sli.do/>) was utilized. This software enhances the participation of the audience, allowing them to ask questions through their mobile devices and vote them. The questions risen were displayed toward a projector, voted by participants and answered during the round table. The software allowed an active participation of the public, that influenced directly the discussion.

Diego Gallo: *A new concept of touristic destination*

In the last decades, globally, the number of tourists has grown significantly. With globalization, becoming successful and attractive touristic destination is getting harder and harder. For these reasons, territorial marketing represents a key element to let people know what a destination can offer, and which are the reasons why people should visit it. The territory, whose values need to be communicated and effectively promoted, is a complex system based on strong relationships between local stakeholders, their activities and the resources. This complex system needs good governance to work smoothly and successfully. One of the most common approaches is defining the success of a tourist destination just in terms of quantity. Probably, this paradigm needs a change, moving from quantity tourism to quality tourism. A successful touristic destination must be saleable to the tourist, fulfilling these characteristics: requested, tested, granted, integrated, coherent, with future perspective. In this respect, NWFPs can play an important role and be integrated into a strategic territorial marketing strategy. In order to promote the specific

agroforestry product, it's fundamental to: underline its specificities and values, safeguard its diversity, involve not only the actors of the value chain of the specific product but also all the local stakeholders (public sector, retailer, restaurants, hotels, companies,...). It's important to keep in mind that to have a successful destination it is not mandatory or enough to have an excellent product: what is needed is an excellent organization of the touristic destination. In this regard, trademarks and brand can definitely have a role in enhancing the visibility and recognition of a destination but they have always to be supported by investments in social and human capital.

Figure 1. Structure of new concept of territorial marketing strategy.

Sara Covi: *Strada della Mela e dei Sapori delle valli di Non e di Sol*
 Best practice described through factsheet and infographic (page 25-27)

The Val di Non and Val di Sole Apples and Flavours Route (*Strada della Mela e dei Sapori delle valli di Non e di Sole*) is one of the best-practices invited at the event. The case study is in Trentino Alto Adige, an Italian region within the Alps, well known as a tourist destination for its mountain trails and hundreds of miles of ski slopes. “*Strada della Mela e dei Sapori delle valli di Non e di Sole*” aims to diversify the tourism offer, integrating actors and stakeholders of typical local agro-food supply chains, such as apples and aromatic plants, This success of this initiative is due mainly to a well-designed territorial marketing strategy, that is multidisciplinary and capable of including all regional peculiarities, also the gastronomic ones. The territorial brand “*Strada della Mela e dei Sapori delle valli di Non e di Sole*”, in 2018, included 193 members, a management committee made of 9 members and 3 employees. The affiliates pay a fixed fee of 100€ per year, that allows them to be included in the network, that include farms, cheese, and wine producers, agritourism, B&B, hotels, mountain huts, restaurants, bars, associations, and touristic promotion agency (APT). The involvement of all the local stakeholders was fundamental in order to have a common view and shared goals. “*Strada della Mela e dei Sapori delle valli di Non e di Sole*” aims to promote the image and appeal of the area, organizing events and activities all year long, not only during the high tourism season. The affiliates are very heterogeneous and cover different agricultural and forest products: bread, apples, berries, cheeses, honey, aromatic and medicinal plants, beers, meat etc. The participated and commonly chosen marketing strategy helped create consensus within local stakeholders, boosting tourism and profitability of most of the reality of the valley.

Antonio Mortali: Il Fungo di Borgotaro

Best practice described through factsheet and infographic (page 16-18)

Fungo di Borgotaro I.G.P. represents the first European trademark related to a wild forest product, (for porcini mushroom). This best practice is the reason why the CCS was organized in the Taro valley, in Emilia Romagna region, Italy. The area where Borgotaro mushrooms grow is managed by *Consorzio Comunalie Parmensi* and it covers more than 13,000 ha, mostly publicly owned. The European trademark is dated back in 1996 and has a central role in the recognition of the Borgotaro mushrooms as Italian excellence. The integration of the mushrooms in the territorial marketing strategy has been an element of success for the area, that in the mushroom growing season is flooded by pickers and food lovers. The mushrooms are so important that the income from mushroom picking licences and permits (mandatory to harvest in these forests), are way higher than the ones from timber. For instance, in favourable years, such as 2013, the income from permits (61,000 permits) was 921,000 €. In 2018, 16,500 permits were sold, corresponding to 250,000 € of income. Nowadays, mushrooms are the flywheel of the valley's economy, with companies and the tourism sector that benefit from this. Furthermore, the incomes from the permits are used to manage the forests and restore or build new public infrastructures. This case study demonstrates that NWFPs can play a role in territorial marketing, becoming the absolute protagonist of a territory.

Carlo Marenda: Save the Truffle

Best practice described through factsheet and infographic (page 22-24)

“Save the Truffle” is a private initiative born in Langhe (Piedmont Region), an area famous for two gastronomy excellences: wine and truffles. One of the main current problems of the area is the cohabitation between vineyards and forests. In the last 25 years, there has been a reduction of 30% of truffle-growing areas, due to the expansion of vineyards. “Save the Truffle” aims to spread the culture and the traditions related to truffles through education activity in schools, events and field trips. One of the main activities organized is the field trips with international tourists, that are willing to pay for a truffle hunting experience. Part of the incomes of the guided tours (30% on average) is reinvested in land management and in the improvement of the truffle-growing areas, creating the condition to safeguard the natural ecosystem of truffles.

Round table: Integrating NWFPs in territorial marketing

- **Maria Capecchi:** Responsible of the truffle sector in Emilia Romagna Region
- **Pierluigi Fedele:** Captain of Carabinieri forest Corp of Parma
- **Diego Gallo:** expert in territorial Marketing and responsible tourism
- **Sara Covi:** Strada della mela e dei sapori delle valli di Non e di Sole
- **Gabriele Locatelli:** Emilia Romagna Region
- **Nicola Sitta:** mycologists and NWFP expert

Different stakeholders attended the roundtable: public entities, police corps, marketing experts, technicians. One of the crucial aspects that emerged was the need, to include all the local stakeholders in any territorial marketing strategies. Facilitating the discussion between policymakers, local stakeholders, police corps, companies and tourist agencies constitute an important element for having common and shared goals and targets. For instance, the roundtable

was the opportunity for the public sector to realize how the prescriptions related to wild bilberries harvesting techniques are an obstacle for the profitability of this NWFP in the Apennines.

Several questions were asked in relation to the news introduced by the fiscal law, that can be a gamechanger in the national NWFPs sector. In fact, it simplifies the duties of professional and occasional pickers, stimulating the conventional legal market, characterized by regular fiscal documents and traceability. This fact underlines the importance of policymakers and the need for discussion between them, the police corps that will control and the pickers. Also, the preconditions to start initiatives such as *“Strada delle Mele e dei Sapori delle valli di Non e di Sole”* were investigated, understanding that in the specific case, the role of the public sector was essential to fund and support the first phase of the initiative.

To sum up, NWFPs can play an important role and be integrated in territorial marketing strategies, contributing to widening the portfolio of a tourist destination. Anyway, it's important to note that a marketing strategy for a specific local product is not enough to drive the success of a destination, but the key factor is the organization and the efficiency of the whole system around the product itself.

4.2 Take-home messages from the seminar

Main take-home messages from the seminar are summarized as follows (whereas, tips from the seminar are presented in the infographic in page 15):

- From the best cases presented, it emerged that NWFPs can become a flywheel of the economy, contributing to enlarge the tourist portfolio of a destination. Anyway, it is essential to promote synergies among services and products of a territory, in order to increase the social capital and make more attractive the tourism destination, with local fairs and events.
- The organization and the coherence of the tourism destination are much more important than the specific product: stakeholder engagement, also through participatory approaches, is needed. The use of trademarks and labels can play a central role in the communication of the quality of a specific product.
- In NWFPs sector the legal framework has a central role since not appropriate policy can compromise an entire value chain. Therefore, understanding role and needs of each actors included in a specific supply chain is necessary in order to design laws that reflect the view of all of them.
- A label/trademark can contribute to awareness-raising of local minor products. However, behind the label, there should be clear and shared standards, in order to give credibility to the label itself. In the territorial marketing strategy, minor local products can represent an added value and become complementary to the most famous products of a territory.

5. Field trip

5.1 Main contents of field trip

The second day of CCs was dedicated to the field trip for visiting the forest managed by *Consorzio Comunalie Parmensi*. The field trip was led by Antonio Mortali, the technical coordinator of the *Consorzio*. The area managed by *Consorzio* has an extension of more than 13,000ha, and in this forest the mushroom production represents the most valuable production. Mushroom picking activity is allowed to foreigners just with a permit. Whereas, only the citizen of the municipality has the right to pick mushrooms for free. Several topics were treated during the field trip:

- Mycosilviculture;
- Management techniques to boost NWFPs production;
- Integrating NWFPs in territorial marketing;
- Multifunctionality of the forest,
- Tourism in the forest;
- The role of the naturalistic guide, in the context of *Consorzio*.

The forests visited are mainly managed as coppice, whose timber is yearly given to the citizen of the municipality for self-consumption. The main tree species are beeches, chestnuts, oaks and some planted conifers, such as spruces and firs. As said, the area is famous for I.G.P. (European trademark for edible products) of local "porcini" (*Boletus edulis*). Consequently, the forest management is carried out for enhancing the local mushroom production, since the biggest income of the *Consorzio* derives from mushroom picking permits, that range from 200,000 € to 800,000 € depending on the year. Incomes from picking permits are regularly reinvested in improving the forest management, and for the maintaining of public infrastructure. The *Consorzio* carries on other innovative initiatives, such as "The Road of Borgotaro Mushroom", a platform for driving tourists to the most important hotspots of the local mushroom supply chain, such as shops, accommodations and restaurants (included in the *Consorzio*). Apart from the income related to permits, mushroom represents a source of income for the territory also thanks to events such as fairs and all the activities and services utilized by tourists.

Figure 2. Field trip in forests managed by Borgotaro Consortium.

During the visit, it has been highlighted that beech, chestnut and oak forests managed as coppice with saplings (up to 100/ha) with rotation periods of 35 years constitute the most productive management system for mushrooms. The area visited includes beeches, managed as high forest, but it has been highlighted that high stands do not present the best conditions for mushroom production.

5.2 Take-home messages from the field trip

- Active forest management is fundamental for ensuring continued and regular mushroom production. Also, the typology of forest management can affect mushroom production. In order to improve the mushroom production, coppices are more productive than high stands.
- In some contexts, where mushroom represents an important element of the local economy, the forest management plans should tend to favour coppices.
- Mushrooms themselves are not enough to attract tourists. Marketing strategies are fundamental: catchy and regularly updated website, mushroom growth indicator freely available online, involvement of local stakeholders in fairs are just some examples that made Borgotaro a successful and attractive touristic destination.
- A good and structured network among different actors (public and privates) of the area should be considered a key element to make effective the territorial marketing strategy.

6. Summary of inputs described through infographic

TERRITORIAL MARKETING

**INTEGRATING NWFPs
IN TERRITORIAL MARKETING STRATEGIES:
TOP 10 TIPS**

1. Connect to the territory

The value of NWFPs can increase if they are connected to the territory where they are grown and produced.

2. Benefit the local economy

Local restaurants and accommodation facilities add value by using local, certified products, enhancing the local economy.

3. Highlight NWFP attractiveness

The attractiveness of NWFPs can raise the value of a product beyond price alone, so focus on their unique qualities.

4. Invest in design

An appealing brand and logo are essential for market success, while merchandising, such as t-shirts and bags, can be an additional source of income for the company.

5. Use labels of origin and quality

Promote your niche products with labels of origin and quality but also connect them with well-known international standards, such as organic or wild, to increase credibility and recognition.

6. Make the trademark work for you

Include product controls and procedures in your trademark policy document so that the trademark guarantees quality.

7. Get local businesses on board

Labels are a powerful tool, but they need to be established in conjunction with strong partnerships with market operators and retailers.

8. Embed products with services

Businesses for products and services should work together to multiply value as part of a coherent tourist offer.

9. Create tourist opportunities

Integrating NWFPs in a territorial marketing strategy can contribute to an increase in the tourist portfolio of a destination, so make sure NWFPs are on the tourist map.

10. Get back to nature

Experiential tourism based on certified products, such as tours and harvesting activities, attracts people looking to get back to nature, who are more inclined to buy your local wild product.

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Learn more about innovation on NWFPs
www.incredibleforest.net

7. Best practices described by factsheets and infographics

7.1 Il fungo di Borgotaro

The final version of this factsheet will be available at: <https://oppla.eu/casestudy/19799>

Il Fungo di Borgotaro": the first P.G.I. (Protected Geographic Indication) labelled wild mushroom.

Theme & Question:

- Marketing: How to better value the locally produced resource?

Non-wood forest products: Wild Mushrooms & Truffles

Primary non-wood forest product: Wild Mushrooms & Truffles

Type of fact sheet: Practice

Position in the value chain: Marketing & Consumers

Type of data: Success story

Source: Personal communication in an INCREDIBLE event (cross-cutting seminar)

Objective:

In the Modenese Apennine (Italy), since the interest towards traditional forest products (as firewood) is declining, also the active forest management is strongly decreasing, especially in marginal areas. In the Taro Valley, the decreased forest management is compromising the conditions required for the development of Boletus mushrooms, a product consumed and appreciated by the local population for centuries. Therefore, there is a need to find mechanisms to re-activate forest management in the area and restore the favourable environmental conditions for the development of this mushroom.

Country: Italy

Region: Emilia-Romagna

Keywords

- edible mushrooms
- mycosilviculture
- wild mushroom picking
- territorial marketing
- tourism
- promotion
- rural areas

Context

The Borgotaro Consortium was created in 1957 in order to manage the rights of local inhabitants to graze, to harvest fuelwood and to pick wild mushrooms. In 1996 the Borgotaro Mushroom has been awarded the P.G.I. (Protected Geographic Indication). A problem that rose with P.G.I. certification has been the growing demand for certified mushrooms, that cannot be fulfilled by the natural wild production. Indeed, the gradual abandonment of forest activities has contributed to reduce the natural production of mushroom. Furthermore, the P.G.I. certification was not able to bring benefits to all local mushroom stakeholders.

Main results

In order to involve all the local stakeholders included in the mushroom supply chain, the Consortium has developed a web site for presenting the whole system of local mushroom business (including restaurants and shops). In parallel, the Consortium has created “The Road of Borgotaro Mushroom”, an initiative that includes road signs and a virtual platform for guiding tourists to the most important hotspots of the local mushroom world, such as shops, food & lodging facilities (included in the Consortium). In order to enhance wild mushroom productivity, most of the incomes from picking permits are re-invested in forest management, with special regard to mycosilviculture.

Main practical recommendations

The mere presence, even if huge, of recreational wild mushroom pickers in an area, can't bring economic and environmental advantages for the territory. A structured network among different activities of the area should be considered the key element to make really effective the marketing strategy and generate local wealth to residents. Furthermore, this case study demonstrates that the objective of P.G.I. certification should be not only the preservation of a product but also the maintenance of local traditions related to the product.

Impacts and weaknesses

In the Borgotaro Consortium, the forest owners manage an annual revenue between 0.5 and 1.2 million €, while the wild mushroom supply chain can generate additional annual revenues of around 0.5 million € of added value. However, the growing interests to the local mushrooms have contributed to the increment of land price, with less capability of the local inhabitants to purchase forest lands, and to constant competition between professional and recreational pickers.

Future developments

Future goals are the improvement of myco-silviculture techniques and further development of additional marketing/promotional tools. For example, the “Happy ticket” initiative has been recently introduced: visitors staying within the valley overnight are awarded a free picking permit (where 60% is paid by the public administration, 30% by the hotel or B&B and 10% by local association). Moreover, the Borgotaro Mushroom Consortium is working to improve the offer for the tourists entering the region, in order to commercialize daily “wild mushroom packages” during the harvesting season

Organisation:

Consorzio Comunalie Parmensi

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EMILIA-ROMAGNA

TERRITORIAL MARKETING

FUNGO DI BORGOTARO: THE FIRST WILD MUSHROOM PROTECTED GEOGRAPHICAL ORIGIN TRADEMARK IN EUROPE

HOW MUSHROOM BECAME THE MAIN ECONOMIC DRIVER OF AN ITALIAN VALLEY

1. In the Taro Valley (Emilia-Romagna region, Italy), Consorzio Comunalie Parmensi (CCP) is a **public entity** managing more than 13,000 hectares of forest. Due to local traditions relating to mushrooms, public **forest owners developed a management strategy to enhance the wild mushroom productivity** of the forest to benefit the local economy.

3. Annual revenues from commercialisation of recreational wild mushroom **picking permits range between 0.5 and 1.2 M €**, while the wild mushroom supply chain can generate additional annual revenues of around 0.5 M€ of added value. Commercialising products and services can **double revenues for the forest owner**, who can invest in wild mushroom productivity through new myco-silviculture techniques and in public institutions such as schools and hospitals.

2. In 1996, the Borgotaro Mushroom was awarded PGI (Protected Geographical Indication) status. CCP **integrated this trademark into the valley's territorial marketing strategy** in order to attract a new type of consumer who harvests forest mushrooms for recreation. With mushroom tourism increasing rapidly, local forest managers have placed mushroom production as a main objective, **applying myco-silviculture techniques**.

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WEBSITE

Innovative online features, such as updated information on mushroom growing rates in the forest and collection areas, attract users to the website.

SIGNPOSTS

Signs guide pickers and tourists to where they can find local mushrooms, such as shops, accommodation and restaurants.

FINANCIAL MECHANISMS

Revenue from picking permits is reinvested into myco-silviculture and in maintaining public facilities such as schools and hospitals.

In the Taro Valley, revenue from NWFPs exceeds that collected from timber. Mushrooms are so relevant for the local economy that most public properties managed by local consortia follow a myco-silviculture approach, and mushrooms have become the backbone of the territorial marketing strategy.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 774832

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7.2 A trademark for wild bilberries

The final version of this factsheet will be available at: <https://oppla.eu/casestudy/19802>

A trademark for local specialties, including wild bilberries, in a territory famous for parmesan cheese

Theme & Question:

- Marketing: How to better value the locally produced resource?

Non-wood forest products: Wild Nuts & Berries

Primary non-wood forest product: Wild Nuts & Berries

Type of fact sheet: Practice

Position in the value chain: Marketing & Consumers

Type of data: Success story

Source: Personal communication in an INCREDIBLE event (cross-cutting seminar)

Objective:

Emilia Romagna is well known for some gastronomic excellences with European P.O.D. and P.G.I. labels, such as parmesan cheese and balsamic vinegar. However, many other local agro-food supply chains, not recognized with specific labels, do not find adequate visibility in the gastronomic offer of the Region. In order to raise awareness also on these local products, the Modena chamber of commerce decided to create the label "Traditions and Flavours of Modena" that is used to support the promotion of niche gastronomic products, such as wild bilberries of the Modena Apennines.

Country: Italy

Region: Emilia-Romagna

Keywords

- wild harvested
- wild blueberries
- label
- trademark

Context

In the regional context, wild bilberries represent minor products and their economic impact is negligible compared to other local products, such as parmesan cheese. Nevertheless, several small local supply chains are based mainly on *Vaccinium myrtillus* L., a wild bilberry species that finds its natural habitat only in some marginal area in the Apennines.

Main results

Thanks to the collective label/trademark of the Modena chamber of commerce, many local products, such as wild bilberries, gain visibility and their quality is guaranteed by specific procedures and controls. With regard to wild bilberries, in the Apennines of Modena in 2018:

- **141 pickers licenses** were released for the professional harvesting by the local authority "Ente Parchi Emilia Centrale";
- **320 tons** is the amount of wild bilberries harvested and traded by pickers;
- **9 enterprises** (mainly focus on transformation) currently can utilize the label promoted by the local chamber of commerce.

Main practical recommendations

A label/trademark can contribute to awareness-raising of local minor products. However, behind the label, there should be clear and shared standards, in order to give credibility to the label itself. In the territorial marketing strategy, minor local products can represent an added value and become complementary to the most famous products of a territory. Apart from the product itself, it is essential to promote synergies among local networks, in order to increase social capital and make more attractive the tourism destination, with local fairs and events.

Impacts and weaknesses

The trademark was developed also to emphasize and recognize the characteristics of *Vaccinium myrtillus* L., that finds the best natural conditions for its growth in the northern Apennine mountains. The label represents an essential element of the territorial marketing strategy, to improve the image of some local minor products. However, laws, standards, rules and the monitoring activity necessary to maintain a credible trademark can be very expensive and so not suitable for every situation.

Future developments

Most of the final consumers are not able to distinguish the different species of bilberries and their origin: cultivated or wild. For this reason, future specific promotional strategies on bilberries of Modena should focus on increasing the awareness of consumers regarding the characteristics of the product, that distinguish one species from another, and the wild product from the cultivated one. Furthermore, several other activities and specific products based on wild bilberries, such as some cosmetics for facial treatment, will be included in the territorial marketing strategy. Incorporating some of the products that now are under the "Traditions and Flavours of Modena" into more recognizable EU labels is another objective.

Organisation:

Modena Chamber of Commerce

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Further information

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EMILIA-ROMAGNA

TERRITORIAL MARKETING

A TRADEMARK FOR WILD BILBERRIES

HOW TO INTEGRATE WILD PRODUCTS IN THE GASTRONOMY OF THE EMILIA-ROMAGNA REGION (ITALY)

1. Emilia-Romagna region (Italy) is well known for several products of **gastronomic excellence with European origin labels**, such as parmesan cheese, processed meat and balsamic vinegar. Yet many other local food supply chains could have better visibility in the gastronomy of the region.

2. The label "**Traditions and Flavours of Modena**", supported and promoted by the Modena Chamber of Commerce, aims to **promote local niche products**. The label includes wild mountain bilberries and other products, such as chestnuts and potatoes harvested in the Modena territory. **Trademarked products are integrated with the gastronomic offer** of local EU-labelled products, taking advantage of their international visibility and recognised quality.

3. Figures for 2018 are encouraging for the wild-labelled bilberries sector. **9 enterprises** (mainly focusing on transformation) currently utilise the label promoted by the local chamber of commerce. **141 pickers' licenses** were released for professional harvesting **320 tons of wild bilberries** harvested and traded by pickers can use the trademark.

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NICHE PRODUCTS

Promoting local niche gastronomy products of the Modena Appenines, including partnerships with well-known EU-labelled products, is essential for attracting tourists who consume *in situ*.

TRADEMARK

The trademark "Traditions and Flavours of Modena" guarantees that the products comply with strict standards and procedures. A common territorial label, covering several products, is more efficient than single product labels.

LOCAL ECONOMY

Thanks to the trademark, income possibilities also emerged in marginal areas. The labelled products create new business opportunities in the first step of the value chain.

A territorial label increases consumer awareness of the origin and quality of local gastronomy. Thanks to the trademark, local products connected to the territory emerge as a market specialty, creating new income opportunities and contributing to the growth of the region's tourism gastronomy portfolio.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 774832

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7.3 Save the truffle

The final version of this factsheet will be available at: <https://oppla.eu/casestudy/19800>

"Save the Truffle": an initiative to protect and safeguard truffle ecosystems

Theme & Question:

- Ecosystem services: Are there other tools, besides payment for ecosystem services, to reward the multifunctionality provided by forests?

Non-wood forest products: Wild Mushrooms & Truffles

Primary non-wood forest product: Wild Mushrooms & Truffles

Type of fact sheet: Practice

Position in the value chain: Marketing & Consumers

Type of data: Success story

Source: Personal communication in an INCREDIBLE event (cross-cutting seminar)

Objective:

City of Alba (Piedmont region, Italy) and the surrounding area, the Langhe and Roero are well known for wine production and some local gastronomic peculiarities, such as white truffle. Unfortunately, over the past 25 years, against a continuing increase in the value of farming products (grapes for wine and hazelnut for chocolate and sweet) and a consequent expansion of cultivated surface, there has been a 30% reduction in truffle-growing areas. "Save the Truffle" aims to promote alternative activities for recovering old truffle-beds and planting new truffle-generating plants.

Country: Italy

Region: Piedmont

Keywords

- truffles
- edible mushrooms
- ecosystem conservation
- territorial marketing
- environmental guide
- tourism

Context

Truffle, especially the white one, constitutes one of the most outstanding and internationally recognized products of Piedmont and one of the main drivers of tourism for the territory. However, consumers know truffle as a valuable product, but most of them do not know the life cycle behind this product and the strong link between truffles and territory of origin. "Save the Truffle" aims to present truffles with an alternative point of view, not based on the fresh truffle sale.

Main results

"Save the Truffles" is a for-profit private company born in 2015 with the aim of restore and preserve natural truffles ecosystem. It proposes to tourists, a walk into the natural ecosystem of truffle and a real truffle hunt experience. In addition, "Save the Truffle" organizes regular education activities and projects related to preservation and restoration of truffle beds. In four years of project activity, "Save the truffle" has planted around 400 plants, cleaned and managed around 5 hectares of forest in a truffle key, preserved about 3 hectares of forest. Whereas, 600 students and 500 truffle hunters have been involved in the activities organized by "Save the truffle".

Main practical recommendations

"Save the Truffle" is becoming very popular, also abroad, due to numerous partnerships with some international tourism agency and thanks to dedicated articles in some newspapers (New York Times, The Telegraph). Another important key of success of "Save the Truffle" is its strong connection with the projects developed for safeguarding and restoring the truffle ecosystem. In fact, many tours organized by "Save the Truffle" are organized in the restoration project areas, so the tourists can touch with their own hands what the company does in order to safeguard truffles ecosystems. Apart from guided tours, another source of income for the company is merchandising, such as t-shirt or bag.

Impacts and weaknesses

Thanks to the incomes generated by its business, "Save the Truffle" has created a new truffle plantation in the territory of Alba municipality and on the Langhe area. This new plantation will be used for multiple teaching and research activities. Furthermore, in the municipal park, new mycorrhized plants have been planted, to recreate the favourable conditions for truffle growing. These two projects have contributed to create public-private partnerships (municipality-company).

Future developments

The idea behind the project is really simple but effective: explore, through organized visits, the tradition and culture behind truffles. Re-invest the incomes to maintain a favourable ecosystem for truffles appears a very effective marketing strategy. It would be interesting to test similar approaches in other contexts and with other products. In the immediate future, "Save the Truffle" is lobbying for a law concerning the protection of trees with a truffle-like vocation.

Organisation:

Save the Truffle

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Further information

<https://www.savethetruffle.com/en/>

PIEDMONT

TERRITORIAL MARKETING

SAVE THE TRUFFLE: PRESERVING NATURAL TRUFFLE ECOSYSTEMS

GUIDED TOURS TO PROMOTE TRUFFLE CULTURE AND RESTORE THEIR ECOSYSTEMS.

1. The city of Alba, in Piedmont region (Italy), and the surrounding area of Langhe and Roero are well known for wines, hazelnuts and some local gastronomic specialties, such as white truffle. Over the past 25 years, increased wine production has led to a **reduction in truffle forests of almost 30%**.

3. Since 2015, thanks to truffle tourism, "Save the Truffle" has planted around 400 trees, cleaned around 5 hectares of truffle forest and saved around 3 hectares of forest. Almost 600 schoolchildren and 8 truffle hunter associations (about 500 total members) have been involved in **educational activities**. These activities have strengthened relations with local administrations and **converted old traditions into current techniques to manage the forest**.

2. "Save the Truffle" is a for-profit private company which aims to restore and preserve natural truffle ecosystems. The company offers **walks into the forest to hunt for wild truffles** and presents an alternative value chain, not based entirely on final product sales. Part of the revenue is invested in **education activities** in local schools and in **preserving truffle forests**.

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INTERNATIONAL TARGET

"Save the Truffle" gains global visibility through smart use of modern tools (eg. crowdfunding) and subsequent interest from national and international press.

GUIDED TOURS

The company offers customised private experiences suiting consumer needs and expectations. Flexibility is one of the key features of their tours.

BRANDING & MERCHANDISING

An appealing brand and logo are essential to be attractive on the market. Apart from guided tours, another source of income is merchandising, such as t-shirts or bags.

Only active forest management can enhance and sustain wild truffle production. Forest managers should not only seek sustainable forest practices but also financial sustainability to maintain active forest management. Private companies based on tourism can contribute to safeguarding natural truffle ecosystems.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 714952

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Coordinator

Partners

7.4 The Non and Sole valleys territorial marketing strategy

The final version of this factsheet will be available at: <https://oppla.eu/casestudy/19801>

The Val di Non and Val di Sole Apples and Flavours route: a successful territorial marketing strategy

Theme & Question:

- Marketing: How to promote territorial marketing of edible NWFP and their derivatives?

Non-wood forest products: Aromatic & Medicinal Plants, Wild Mushrooms & Truffles
Wild Nuts & Berries

Primary non-wood forest product: Transversal

Type of fact sheet: Practice

Position in the value chain: Marketing & Consumers

Type of data: Success story

Source: Personal communication in an INCREDIBLE event (cross-cutting seminar)

Objective:

Diversify the tourism offer in Trentino Alto-Adige (Italy), a famous destination that attracts thousands of tourists for its mountain trails and hundreds of miles of ski slopes. A diversification of local tourism offer, involving local stakeholders and supported by a specific territorial marketing strategy, can bring benefits to small farmers, restaurants and many other local actors, especially in the marginal area of the region.

Country: Italy

Region: Emilia-Romagna

Keywords

- wild harvested
- wild harvested plants
- orchard plantation
- natural remedies
- territorial marketing
- rural areas
- tourism

Context

Numerous traditional agro-food supply chains, strongly linked with the territory, are present in the area. Some of them are well-structured but, very often, appear isolated and not well connected with the classic tourism offer of Trentino Alto Adige. "The Val di Non and Val di Sole Apples and Flavours route" is a mixed public (tourism office)/private(local companies-facilities) initiative created to connect (by a virtual road) the different local producers and promote an alternative tourism offer, involving all actors included in some specific local agro-food supply chains.

Main results

"The Val di Non and Val di Sole Apples and Flavours route" was designed to integrate the offer of agricultural and wild products, food and wine, hotels and restaurants under one all-embracing itinerary. Apples constitute the most famous product of these valleys, but many others, such as aromatic & medicinal plants, cheeses are involved in the activities carried on by the "route". Food and board facilities, farms, companies and all stakeholders should pay a fix annual fee (around 100 €) to join the route, that will promote their products and services during local events and fair. To date more than 200 companies are included in the "route", whose activities animated the valley throughout the year.

Main practical recommendations

The success of "The Val di Non and Val di Sole Apples and Flavours route" demonstrates that the synergies between the public sector (tourist promotion agency) and private companies are essential to diversify the classic tourism offer of a region. The branding of a territory should be comprehensive and multidisciplinary, including all its peculiarities, also the gastronomic ones. Besides, this case shows how the interest in rural tourism, is continuously increasing. This typology of tourism should be considered complementary, and not alternative with respect to the traditional tourism offer.

Impacts and weaknesses

With a low annual fee, organizations/companies (regardless the size), can join a structured network, capable of ensuring visibility and numerous opportunities for partnerships. The activities organized by "The Val di Non and Val di Sole Apples and Flavours route" contribute to animate the area all year long and not only during peak tourism season. Right now, the leading partner of the initiative is represented by an entity, made up by public and private companies. This can be a weakness since specific political interests can obstacle the correct development of the initiative.

Future developments

To date, apples constitute the real driver of "The Val di Non and Val di Sole Apples and Flavours route". However, even now, the network includes actors and supply chains from other local products, such as chestnuts and aromatic & medicinal plants, wines, processed meat and many more. In the close future, the initiative will organize more activities and keep animating and promoting the valleys, maintaining and increasing its attractiveness.

Organisation:

The Val di Non and Val di Sole Apples and Flavours route

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Further information

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TRENTINO ALTO-ADIGE

TERRITORIAL MARKETING

**THE NON AND SOLE VALLEYS
TERRITORIAL MARKETING STRATEGY**

APPLES AS A DRIVING FORCE FOR THE LOCAL ECONOMY ALL YEAR ROUND

1. Apples in the Non and Sole valleys (Trentino Alto-Adige region, Italy) represent the main driving force of the local economy, with exports globally thanks to their EU label. Traditionally an agricultural crop, apples were not previously considered a potential tourist attraction and tourism flow in these valleys was mainly seasonal, concentrated in summer (trekking) and winter (skiing).

3. Thanks to the "route", tourism opportunities are available throughout the year, creating networks among local actors and improving the appeal as a tourist destination. Now, tourists can enjoy the flowering of apple trees in springtime and participate in harvesting activities in the autumn. In 2018 there were 193 members of the "route" and the main event, an apple fair, attracted almost 20,000 tourists in autumn.

2. "The Val di Non and Val di Sole Apples and Flavours route" is a mixed public/private initiative based on partnership between the provincial tourism associations and local stakeholders. It offers various activities, such as events, fairs and field trips, related to local specialties: apples, berries, cheeses, aromatic & medicinal plants, etc. By paying just 100€ annually to the "route", local actors can be involved as hosts, promoters and suppliers in these events, enlarging their business and promoting their specialties.

INTEGRATING TOURISM AND GASTRONOMY: TOP TIPS FOR SUCCESS!

PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL

Attractive information and promotional materials easily available both online and in tourist offices are essential. The "route" website offers an updated web-map showing participating facilities/shops .

RICHNESS OF THE OFFER

A rich and varied offer connecting producers, food & lodging facilities and retailers in an appealing network. Everyone can find the activity that best meets their needs, all year round.

TYPICAL EXPERIENCES

Today tourists don't just look for beautiful places but for authentic experiences. The "route" proposes a variety of experiences and events connected to local traditions.

With successful territorial marketing, local supply chains benefit from increased tourist flow and its related income throughout the year. Tourism demand is increasing globally: proposing something authentic locally is essential to emerge in the market.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 774812

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